

WORKLOAD, OCCUPATIONAL STRESS, MENTAL WELL-BEING AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance of public school teachers in the Division of Bohol. A quantitative research design was employed, using validated survey questionnaires to collect data from teachers across various districts during S.Y. 2025–2026. The instruments measured workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance, while descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation were applied to analyze the data. Results revealed that teachers experienced high workloads due to extended teaching hours, administrative paperwork, and co-curricular duties. Occupational stress was moderate, with emotional exhaustion as the most prevalent dimension, compounded by role overload and limited institutional support. Despite these challenges, teachers demonstrated high levels of mental well-being, reflecting resilience and coping strategies, though their work-life balance remained moderate, indicating difficulty in harmonizing professional and personal roles. Correlation analysis confirmed that workload and occupational stress were negatively associated with work-life balance, while mental well-being showed a significant positive relationship and emerged as the strongest predictor. The study concludes that excessive workload and stress undermine teachers' work-life balance, but strong mental well-being enhances resilience and balance. It recommends strict enforcement of the Magna Carta's six-hour teaching limit, reassignment of ancillary tasks to administrative staff, streamlining of DepEd reporting systems, and integration of wellness and mental health programs to sustain teacher well-being and improve instructional quality.

Keywords: *Workload; Occupational Stress; Mental Well-Being; Work-Life Balance; Public School Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is widely recognized as one of the most essential yet demanding professions, as teachers play a critical role in shaping the intellectual and moral foundations of society. In recent decades, the complexity of the teaching profession has intensified due to increasing instructional expectations, administrative responsibilities, and accountability demands. These conditions have contributed to the growing recognition of teaching as a high-stress occupation, raising concerns about teachers' well-being and their ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance (Kyriacou, 2011; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). In line with this, improving teacher welfare is increasingly viewed as a fundamental component of educational quality, as emphasized in recent frameworks on enhancing basic education standards, which highlight that sustainable quality advancement depends on supporting teachers' professional and personal well-being (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024).

These challenges are further exacerbated by systemic issues such as large class sizes, extensive paperwork, and numerous non-teaching assignments that extend beyond official working hours. Empirical evidence indicates that Filipino teachers devote a substantial portion of their time to administrative and clerical tasks, often limiting the time available for instructional activities and professional engagement (Bayudan-Dacuycuy et al., 2020; Taguma & Barrera, 2019). Despite existing legal frameworks such as the *Magna Carta for Public School Teachers* and the *Mental Health Act*, concerns regarding excessive workload, role ambiguity, and insufficient institutional support continue to persist (Ancho & Bongco, 2019; Simbre et al., 2021; Samaniego, 2022).

Workload in the teaching profession has evolved into a multidimensional construct that extends beyond classroom instruction. Teachers are expected to engage in lesson planning, assessment, documentation, co-curricular supervision, and community involvement, often resulting in extended working hours and increased work demands (Kyriacou, 2011). Globally, teachers spend an average of over 40 hours per week on work-related tasks, with a significant proportion dedicated to non-teaching responsibilities. Several studies have shown that teachers frequently exceed prescribed working hours due to documentation requirements and digital reporting systems, which contribute to fatigue, reduced efficiency, and declining job satisfaction (Butt & Lance, 2005). The increasing integration of digital technologies has further intensified workload demands, blurring the boundaries between professional and personal life (Talidad & Toquero, 2020).

Closely associated with workload is occupational stress, which refers to the psychological and physiological responses arising when job demands exceed an individual's capacity to cope (Cohen et al., 1983). Teachers are consistently identified among the most stress-prone professionals due to the emotional, cognitive, and social demands of their work (Kyriacou, 2011; Hakanen et al., 2024). Occupational stress among teachers is commonly manifested through emotional exhaustion, role overload, role conflict, and perceived lack of institutional support. Emotional exhaustion, a key

component of burnout, results from prolonged exposure to demanding work conditions, while role overload and role conflict emerge from excessive and competing responsibilities (Maslach & Jackson, 2013). The consequences of excessive workload and occupational stress are closely linked to teachers' mental well-being and their capacity to maintain work-life balance. Mental well-being encompasses psychological functioning, emotional stability, and a sense of purpose, all of which are essential for effective teaching and personal fulfillment (Gu & Day, 2010). However, sustained exposure to high work demands and stress can deplete teachers' emotional and cognitive resources, resulting in burnout, reduced motivation, and diminished overall well-being (Hakanen & Kaltainen, 2026). In parallel, work-life balance—defined as the ability to effectively manage professional and personal roles (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011)—is often disrupted when work demands encroach upon personal time. Teachers frequently report difficulty maintaining this balance due to extended working hours, constant communication demands, and cultural expectations that emphasize dedication to service (Aquino et al., 2023).

The interplay among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance has been widely acknowledged in the literature. Excessive workload increases stress levels, which in turn negatively affects mental well-being and disrupts the equilibrium between work and personal life. Conversely, supportive work environments and manageable workloads contribute to reduced stress and improved well-being (Wang, 2024). The Job Demand–Control Model (Karasek, 1979) explains how high job demands coupled with low autonomy lead to psychological strain, while Kahn et al. (1964) highlight the stress arising from multiple and conflicting responsibilities. Similarly, Hobfoll (1989) emphasizes the depletion of personal resources under prolonged stress, and Greenhaus and Allen (2011) underscore the importance of achieving equilibrium between professional and personal domains.

Despite the extensive body of literature on these variables, existing studies have largely examined workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance in isolation. There remains a paucity of research that comprehensively investigates their interrelationships, particularly within localized contexts such as Bohol. This gap limits the understanding of how these factors collectively influence teachers' professional experiences and overall well-being.

In response, this study aimed to determine the relationships among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance of public school teachers. By providing empirical evidence on how these variables interact, the study sought to inform policy development and institutional practices that support teacher welfare. Ultimately, understanding these dynamics was essential for promoting sustainable teaching conditions, enhancing job satisfaction, and ensuring the delivery of quality education in public schools.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being and work-life balance of public-school teachers for SY: 2025-2026.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. civil status;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. teaching position;
 - 1.5. current length of service; and
 - 1.6. number of teaching loads;
2. What is the level of workload of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. teaching load;
 - 2.2. administrative and clerical tasks;
 - 2.3. co-curricular and community-related duties; and
 - 2.4. time spent beyond official working hours?
3. What is the level of occupational stress of public-school teachers with respect to:
 - 3.1. emotional exhaustion;
 - 3.2. role overload;
 - 3.3. role conflict; and
 - 3.4. lack of institutional support?
4. What is the level of mental well-being of the respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1. psychological Functioning;
 - 4.2. emotional Balance
 - 4.3. life Satisfaction and Sense of Purpose?
5. What is the level of work-life balance of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 5.1. time balance;
 - 5.2. involvement balance; and
 - 5.3. satisfaction balance between work and personal life?
6. Is there a significant relationship in terms of:
 - 6.1 work-life balance and workload among public school teachers?
 - 6.2 work-life and occupational stress among public school teachers?
 - 6.3 work-life and mental well-being among public school teachers?
7. What action can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design to determine the levels of workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance among public school teachers. The design involved the collection and analysis of numerical data using standardized survey instruments, allowing the variables under study to be measured objectively and systematically. Through this approach, the study was able to describe the extent of each variable and examine the statistical relationships among workload,

occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance. By utilizing quantitative methods, the study generated empirical evidence that served as the basis for data-driven

Research Environment

The study was conducted in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Bohol under the Department of Education. Bohol, located in Central Visayas, includes both rural and urban school settings with varied institutional and community conditions. This context provided an appropriate environment for examining workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance among teachers.

Research Participants

The respondents of the study were public elementary school teachers from 90 selected schools across the three Congressional Districts in the Division of Bohol during the School Year 2025–2026. A total of 596 teachers participated in the study. The sample size was determined using RStudio at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error to ensure statistical reliability. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to proportionally represent teachers from each district.

Distributions of Respondents

Congressional Districts (CD)	No. of Schools	No. Of Teachers
CD 1	23	143
CD 2	34	234
CD3	33	216
TOTAL	90	596

Research Instrument

A modified questionnaire served as the primary data-gathering instrument to measure workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance. The instrument consisted of four components: (1) a workload scale adapted from the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2009); (2) an occupational stress scale based on the Perceived Stress Scale developed by Cohen et al. (1983); (3) a mental well-being scale adapted from the Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (Stewart-Brown & Janmohamed, 2008); and (4) a work-life balance scale based on the model developed by Hayman (2005).

All items were measured using a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The instrument was contextualized to align with the conditions of the respondents. Content validity was established through expert review, while reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with coefficients meeting the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory internal consistency (Taber, 2018).

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, approval was secured from the Vice President for Academic and Quality Assurance and the Dean of the School of Advanced Studies at Bohol Island State University, as well as permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd–Bohol, Public Schools District Supervisors, and school heads. Survey questionnaires were then distributed to the selected respondents. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, and informed consent was obtained prior to participation. Retrieved data were coded, tallied, and subjected to statistical analysis. Ethical standards were strictly observed. Participation was voluntary, responses were kept confidential and anonymous, and data were securely stored.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study were organized, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools. Descriptive statistics were primarily employed to determine the levels of teachers' workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance.

Specifically, the weighted mean was used to measure the average responses of the participants for each variable and to describe the level of workload, level of occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance. The computed means were interpreted using the four-point Likert scale provided in the research instrument.

To examine the relationships among the variables, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was utilized to determine the significant relationship between teachers' workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance.

All statistical computations were performed using appropriate statistical software, and the level of significance was set at 0.05 to test the hypotheses of the study.

The researcher utilized a modified questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. It is composed of four parts:

Workload Scale. Adapted from the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) framework developed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2009), this instrument assesses teaching load, administrative and clerical tasks, co-curricular duties, and time spent beyond regular working hours. The scale utilizes a four-point Likert format to determine the extent of workload experienced by teachers, interpreted as follows:

Level of Teachers' Workload

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Teachers have a very high workload.
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	Teachers have a high workload.
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Teachers have a moderate workload.
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Teachers have a low workload.

Occupational Stress Scale. Adapted from the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) developed by Cohen et al. (1983), measuring emotional exhaustion, role overload, role conflict, and perceived lack of institutional support. The instrument uses a four-point Likert scale to determine the extent of workload experienced by teachers, interpreted as follows:

Level of Teachers' Occupational Stress

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Teachers experience high stress.
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	Teachers experience moderate stress.
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Teachers experience low stress.
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Teachers experience no stress.

Mental Well-Being Scale. Adapted from the Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale developed by Stewart-Brown and Janmohamed (2008), this instrument assesses the level of mental well-being of public school teachers in terms of psychological functioning, emotional balance, and perceived life satisfaction. The scale utilizes a four-point Likert format to determine the extent of mental well-being experienced by teachers, interpreted as follows:

Level of Teachers' Mental Well-being

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Teachers demonstrate excellent mental well-being; they effectively manage stress, maintain positive emotions, and function optimally in personal and professional life.
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	Teachers show good mental well-being; they are generally able to cope with stress and maintain a healthy emotional and psychological state.
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Teachers exhibit signs of difficulty in managing stress and maintaining emotional balance; mental well-being may be affected.
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Teachers have poor mental well-being; they may struggle significantly with stress, emotions, and daily functioning.

Work-Life Balance Scale. Adapted from the model developed by Hayman (2005), this instrument assesses teachers' work-life balance in terms of time balance, involvement balance, and satisfaction balance in managing professional and personal responsibilities. The scale utilizes a four-point Likert format to determine the extent of work-life balance experienced by teachers, interpreted as follows:

Level of Teachers' Work-life Balance

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Teachers have high work-life balance.
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	Teachers have moderate work-life balance.
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Teachers have low work-life balance.
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Teachers have no work-life balance.

RESULTS

This section presents and analyzes the data in accordance with the objectives of the study. The findings are organized based on the key variables, including demographic profile, workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, work-life balance, and the relationships among these variables. Statistical results are interpreted using established criteria and supported by relevant theoretical perspectives.

Table 1
DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS
n= 596

1.1 Age		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	30 – 39	222	37.20%	1
	40 – 49	200	33.60%	2
	50 – 59	111	18.62%	3
	20 – 29	48	8.10%	4
	60 years old and above	14	2.30%	5
	30 – 39	1	0.20%	6
1.2 Civil Status		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Married	495	83.05%	1
	Single	83	13.93%	2
	Widowed	12	2.01%	3
	Separated	6	1.01%	4
1.3 Highest Educational Attainment		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Master's Degree units	246	41.28%	1
	Bachelor's Degree	193	32.38%	2
	Master's Degree	110	18.46%	3
	Doctorate units	34	5.70%	4
	Doctorate (PhD/EdD)	13	2.18%	5
1.4 Current Teaching Position		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Teacher III	385	64.60%	1
	Teacher I	141	23.66%	2
	Master Teacher I	32	5.37%	3
	Teacher II	19	3.19%	4
	Master Teacher 2 or Higher	9	1.51%	5
	Special Science Teacher I	3	0.50%	6
	SNED TEACHER 1	1	0.17%	7
	SPST-I	2	0.34%	8.5

Province Paid Teacher	2	0.34%	8.5
Teacher 6	2	0.34%	8.5
1.5 Length of Service in Teaching	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
10 - 14 years	156	26.17%	1
20 years and above	136	22.82%	2
5 - 9 years	132	22.15%	3
Less than 5 years	89	14.93%	4
15-19 years	83	13.93%	5
1.6 Number of Teaching Loads per Week (Class Hours)	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
31 hours and above	242	40.60%	1
26 - 30 hours	202	33.89%	2
15-20 hours	86	14.43%	3
21-25 hours	66	11.07%	4
Total	596	100	

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service, and number of teaching loads.

In terms of age, the majority of respondents were within the 30–39 age group (37.20%), followed by those aged 40–49 (33.60%) and 50–59 (18.62%). This indicates that most respondents are in their mid-career stage. Regarding civil status, a large proportion were married (83.05%), suggesting that most respondents have family responsibilities alongside their professional roles.

With respect to educational attainment, the highest proportion had Master's Degree units (41.28%), followed by those with a Bachelor's Degree (32.38%) and those who had completed a Master's Degree (18.46%). This implies that most teachers are academically advancing, reflecting professional growth and compliance with educational standards.

In terms of teaching position, the majority were Teacher III (64.60%), followed by Teacher I (23.66%). This indicates that most respondents have progressed within the teaching ranks, signifying experience and tenure in the profession.

For length of service, the largest group had 10–14 years of teaching experience (26.17%), followed by those with 20 years and above (22.82%) and 5–9 years (22.15%). This further supports that the respondents are generally experienced teachers.

Regarding teaching load, a significant number handled 31 hours and above per week (40.60%), while 33.89% handled 26–30 hours. This suggests that the majority of teachers carry heavy teaching loads.

Overall, the results indicate that the respondents are predominantly mid-career, professionally established teachers who are managing substantial teaching responsibilities. The combination of experience, professional rank, and high teaching

loads suggests that workload demands are a consistent and structural condition among public school teachers in the study.

Table 2
LEVEL OF WORKLOAD OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

A. Teaching Load	Mean	INT	RANK
1. I spend a significant amount of time preparing daily lesson plans and instructional materials.	3.26	High	1
2. Large class sizes increase my teaching workload and pose additional challenges in classroom management.	2.95	High	2
3. My teaching schedule requires me to handle more classes than I can effectively manage.	2.69	High	3
4. The number of studies assigned to me often exceeds what I can handle effectively.	2.61	High	4
5. I teach subjects or grade levels outside my specialization due to staffing shortages.	2.53	High	5
Composite Mean	2.81	High	
B. Administrative and Clerical Tasks			
6. I spend a considerable amount of time completing reports, forms, and other administrative documents.	3.13	High	1
7. The amount of paperwork required by DepEd and the school is excessive.	2.89	High	2
8. Administrative compliance requirements take time away from actual teaching.]	2.83	High	3
9. Administrative duties often interfere with my preparation for teaching in the classroom.	2.76	High	4
10. I am frequently tasked with clerical work that is not directly related to my teaching responsibilities.	2.55	High	5
Composite Mean	2.83	High	
C. Co-Curricular and Related Duties			
11. I sometimes decline personal or family commitments due to school-related events or programs.	3.10	High	1
12. I am expected to participate in numerous co-curricular and extracurricular activities.	3.06	High	2
13. Co-curricular responsibilities significantly increase my overall workload.	2.90	High	3
14. I am involved in community extension programs or activities organized by the school.	2.87	High	4
15. I am often required to attend seminars, training sessions, or meetings outside of regular work hours.	2.84	High	5
Composite Mean			
D. Time Spent Beyond Official Working Hours	3.13	High	
16. I often bring schoolwork home to finish reports or lesson plans.	3.33	High	1
17. I regularly work on weekends to complete school-related tasks.	3.16	High	2
18. I spend more than six hours a day on classroom teaching and related activities.	3.20	High	3
19. My working hours extend far beyond the official six-hour teaching requirement stated in the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (R.A. 4670).	3.06	High	4
20. I rarely have free time after school hours because of unfinished tasks.	2.91	High	5
Composite Mean	3.13	High	
Grand Mean	2.93	High	

Table 2 presents the level of workload of public school teachers, with a grand mean of 2.93, interpreted as high level, indicating that teachers generally experience a considerable workload across all dimensions.

In terms of Teaching Load, the composite mean of 2.81 (high) shows that instructional responsibilities are demanding. The highest mean (3.26) indicates that preparing daily lesson plans and instructional materials is the most time-consuming task, while the lowest mean (2.53) suggests that teaching outside one’s specialization is less frequent but still contributes to the workload.

For Administrative and Clerical Tasks, the composite mean of 2.83 (high) reflects the significant burden of non-teaching responsibilities. The highest mean (3.13) reveals that completing reports and documents requires substantial time, while the lowest mean (2.55) indicates that clerical tasks unrelated to teaching, although less frequent, still add to workload demands.

In Co-Curricular and Related Duties, results indicate a high level of workload, with the highest mean (3.10) showing that teachers often sacrifice personal or family commitments due to school activities. The lowest mean (2.84) suggests that attending seminars and training outside regular hours, while still demanding, is relatively less burdensome compared to other responsibilities.

Notably, Time Spent Beyond Official Working Hours recorded the highest composite mean of 3.13 (high), indicating that teachers frequently extend their work beyond mandated hours. The highest mean (3.33) shows that teachers often bring work home, while the lowest mean (2.91) indicates limited free time due to unfinished tasks.

Overall, the findings reveal that teachers experience a high and multidimensional workload, with the most significant burden arising from work extending beyond official hours. This suggests that workload demands are not confined to classroom instruction but are intensified by administrative tasks and additional responsibilities, contributing to prolonged working hours and reduced personal time.

Table 3
LEVEL OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS TEACHERS

A. Emotional Exhaustion	Mean	Level	RANK
1. I feel emotionally exhausted after a day of teaching.	3.05	Moderate	1
2. I find it challenging to recover energy after school hours.	3.04	Moderate	2
3. I feel drained by the effort it takes to prepare lessons, handle students, and meet deadlines.	3.01	Moderate	3
4. I feel overwhelmed by the emotional demands of my students and colleagues.	2.97	Moderate	4
5. I often feel too tired to do things that I enjoy outside of work.	2.86	Moderate	5
Composite Mean	2.98	Moderate	
B. Role Overload			
6. There is often not enough time to complete all my teaching-related tasks.	2.82	Moderate	1

7. I have too many responsibilities at school to perform them all well.	2.72	Moderate	2
8. I frequently work under time pressure due to multiple deadlines.	2.68	Moderate	3
9. I am expected to handle more work than my position requires.	2.66	Moderate	4
10. My workload is beyond what one Teacher can reasonably handle.	2.61	Moderate	5
Composite Mean	2.70	Moderate	
C. Role Conflict			
11. I am sometimes torn between following school directives and meeting the needs of my students.	2.65	Moderate	1
12. I feel pressured to comply with policies that conflict with my professional judgment.	2.58	Moderate	2
13. I experience difficulty balancing teaching, administrative, and community roles.	2.56	Moderate	3
14. I am uncertain about what is expected of me in my job.	2.46	Moderate	4
15. I receive conflicting instructions from school administrators or supervisors.	2.35	Moderate	5
Composite Mean	2.52	Moderate	
D. Lack of Institutional Support			
16. My school lacks programs to help teachers manage stress or maintain well-being.	2.46	Moderate	1
17. I rarely receive recognition or appreciation for the work I do.	2.42	Moderate	2
18. The school rarely provides adequate materials or resources needed for effective teaching.	2.39	Moderate	3
19. As a teacher, my concerns and suggestions are not taken seriously by the administration.	2.24	Moderate	4
16. My school administration does not provide enough support for teachers' well-being.	2.23	Moderate	5
Composite Mean	2.35	Moderate	
Grand Mean	2.64	Moderate	

Table 3 presents the level of occupational stress of public school teachers, with a grand mean of 2.64, interpreted as moderate level, indicating that teachers experience a noticeable but manageable degree of stress across all dimensions.

In terms of Emotional Exhaustion, the composite mean of 2.98 (moderate) indicates that teachers frequently experience fatigue and emotional strain. The highest mean (3.05) shows that teachers feel emotionally exhausted after a day of teaching, while the lowest mean (2.86) suggests that fatigue affecting personal activities is present but relatively less intense. This dimension emerged as the highest among the four, indicating that emotional demands are the most prominent source of stress.

For Role Overload, the composite mean of 2.70 (moderate) reflects that teachers experience pressure from multiple responsibilities. The highest mean (2.82) indicates insufficient time to complete teaching-related tasks, while the lowest mean (2.61) suggests that perceiving workload as beyond reasonable capacity is slightly less emphasized, though still evident.

In Role Conflict, the composite mean of 2.52 (moderate) shows that teachers encounter challenges in balancing competing expectations. The highest mean (2.65)

indicates tension between following school directives and addressing student needs, while the lowest mean (2.35) reflects that conflicting instructions from administrators occur less frequently but still contribute to stress.

For Lack of Institutional Support, the composite mean of 2.35 (moderate) indicates that teachers perceive limited organizational support. The highest mean (2.46) suggests insufficient programs for stress management and well-being, while the lowest mean (2.23) points to inadequate administrative support as a continuing concern.

Overall, the findings reveal that teachers experience moderate occupational stress, with emotional exhaustion as the most dominant dimension and lack of institutional support as the least, yet still significant, factor. This suggests that while teachers demonstrate resilience in managing their responsibilities, the emotional demands of teaching and the accumulation of role-related pressures remain key contributors to their stress levels. These findings are supported by prior research which emphasizes that teaching is a high-stress profession characterized by emotional demands, workload pressures, and role-related challenges, with emotional exhaustion identified as a central component of teacher stress (Kyriacou, 2011).

Table 4
LEVEL OF MENTAL WELL- BEING OF RESPONDENTS

A. Psychological Well-Being	Mean	INT	RANK
1. I am able to think clearly and make sound decisions in my daily work.	3.22	High	1
2. I feel capable of managing my responsibilities as a teacher.	3.21	High	2
3. I feel motivated to perform my work despite challenges.]	3.18	High	3
4. I feel confident in handling challenges that arise in my teaching responsibilities.	3.16	High	4
5. I am able to concentrate well when performing my tasks at school.	3.15	High	5
Composite Mean	3.19	High	
B. Emotional Balance			
6. I feel hopeful about my personal and professional future.	3.21	High	1
7. I feel emotionally supported by people around me.	3.16	High	2
8. I am able to recover emotionally after stressful workdays.	3.11	High	3
9. I generally feel calm and emotionally stable during the school week.	3.09	High	4
10. I am able to regulate my emotions even when work becomes demanding.	3.08	High	5
Composite Mean	3.13	High	
C. Life satisfaction & sense of purpose			
11. I find meaning and purpose in my role as a teacher.	3.28	High	1.5
12. I feel that my work contributes positively to my personal growth.	3.28	Very High	1.5
13. I feel satisfied with my life as a whole.	3.24	High	3
14. I feel that my life is balanced and worthwhile.	3.16	High	4
15. I am able to enjoy life outside of my work responsibilities.	3.15	High	5
Composite Mean	3.22	High	
Grand Mean	3.18	High	

Table 4 presents the level of mental well-being of the respondents, with a grand mean of 3.18, interpreted as high level, indicating that teachers generally maintain positive mental well-being across all dimensions.

In terms of Psychological Well-Being, the composite mean of 3.19 (high) indicates that teachers demonstrate strong cognitive functioning and professional competence. The highest mean (3.22) shows that teachers are able to think clearly and make sound decisions, while the lowest mean (3.15) suggests that concentration in performing tasks, although still high, is relatively less pronounced. This implies that teachers are generally resilient and capable in managing their responsibilities.

For Emotional Balance, the composite mean of 3.13 (high) reflects that teachers maintain a generally positive emotional state. The highest mean (3.21) indicates that teachers feel hopeful about their personal and professional future, while the lowest mean (3.08) suggests that regulating emotions under demanding situations is comparatively more challenging. This indicates that while teachers remain emotionally stable, managing stress-related emotions requires continuous effort.

In Life Satisfaction and Sense of Purpose, the composite mean of 3.22 (high) reveals that teachers derive strong meaning and fulfillment from their profession. The highest mean (3.28), interpreted as very high, indicates that teachers find purpose in their role and perceive their work as contributing to personal growth. The lowest mean (3.15) shows that enjoyment of life outside work, although still high, is slightly less emphasized. This suggests that professional purpose is a key driver of teachers' well-being.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers exhibit high mental well-being, with life satisfaction and sense of purpose as the strongest dimension and emotional balance as the lowest, though still high. This implies that teachers draw resilience and motivation from the meaning they attach to their profession, enabling them to maintain psychological functioning despite work demands. These findings are supported by previous research which indicates that teachers can sustain positive mental well-being through resilience, coping strategies, and a strong sense of purpose, even in demanding work environments (Klassen & Chiu, 2010).

Table 5
LEVEL OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

A. Time Balance	Mean	INT	RANK
1. I allocate enough time to both my teaching duties and my personal/family life.	3.12	Moderate	1
2. My work schedule rarely prevents me from attending important family or personal events.	2.85	Moderate	2
3. I often have to sacrifice my personal time because of unexpected school demands.	2.96	Moderate	3
4. My weekly schedule allows me to rest and recover after work.	2.72	Moderate	4
5. I have sufficient free time to pursue personal interests outside teaching.	2.55	Moderate	5
6. I can finish my work within official working hours without regularly taking work home.	2.49	Moderate	6
Composite Mean	2.75	Moderate	
B. Involvement Balance			
7. I can invest adequate emotional energy in both work and personal relationships.	2.88	Moderate	1

8. I can engage fully in my family or community roles after finishing work.	2.83	Moderate	2
9. I find it easy to switch my focus from school responsibilities to home responsibilities when needed.	2.77	Moderate	3
10. I can participate in household/community activities without worrying about unfinished school tasks.	2.60	Moderate	4
11. I often feel torn between my teaching responsibilities and personal commitments.	2.23	Low	5
12. Work obligations often interfere with my ability to be present for my family.	2.10	Low	6
Composite Mean	2.57	Moderate	
C. Satisfaction Balance			
13. I feel fulfilled both as a teacher and in my personal life.]	3.01	Moderate	1
14. Overall, I am satisfied with how my professional and personal roles align with each other.	2.90	Moderate	2
15. I am satisfied with the balance between my job and my personal life.	2.88	Moderate	3
16. My current work arrangements allow me to achieve my personal life goals.]	2.87	Moderate	4
17. My work-life balance is poor.]	2.50	Moderate	5
18. I often regret the amount of time I spend on work instead of my personal life.	2.40	Low	6
Composite Mean	2.76	Moderate	
Grand Mean	2.74	Moderate	

Table 5 presents the level of work-life balance of public school teachers, with a grand mean of 2.74, interpreted as moderate level, indicating that teachers are able to maintain balance between work and personal life to some extent, although challenges remain across all dimensions.

In terms of Time Balance, the composite mean of 2.75 (moderate) suggests that teachers are able to allocate time for both professional and personal responsibilities. The highest mean (3.12) indicates that teachers manage to allot time for teaching and family life, while the lowest mean (2.49) reveals difficulty in completing work within official hours without bringing tasks home. This implies that personal time and rest are often compromised due to extended work demands.

For Involvement Balance, the composite mean of 2.57 (moderate) reflects that teachers moderately manage their emotional engagement in both work and personal roles. The highest mean (2.88) indicates that teachers can invest emotional energy in both domains, while the lowest mean (2.10), interpreted as low, shows that work obligations frequently interfere with their ability to be present for their families. This makes involvement balance the weakest dimension, highlighting challenges in maintaining emotional presence in personal life.

In Satisfaction Balance, the composite mean of 2.76 (moderate) indicates that teachers are moderately satisfied with how their professional and personal roles align. The highest mean (3.01) shows that teachers feel fulfilled in both domains, while the lowest mean (2.40), interpreted as low, suggests that many teachers experience regret

over the time spent on work instead of personal life. This indicates that although satisfaction is present, concerns about imbalance persist.

Overall, the findings reveal that teachers' work-life balance is moderate, with time and satisfaction balance slightly higher than involvement balance. While teachers are able to manage their roles to some degree, their emotional involvement in family and personal life is the most affected, largely due to work-related demands. These findings are supported by previous studies which indicate that teachers often experience difficulty maintaining work-life balance due to workload pressures and overlapping responsibilities, leading to reduced personal time and family engagement (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011).

Table 6
SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP AMONG THE VARIABLES

Variables	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
1. Workload and work-life balance	-0.128	.002	Very weak negative correlation	Reject Ho
2. Occupational Stress and Work-Life Balance	-0.228	.001	Weak negative correlation	Reject Ho
3. Mental Well-Being and Worklife Balance	0.547	.001	Moderate positive correlation	Reject Ho

Table 6 presents the significant relationships among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance. The results show that all variables are significantly related to work-life balance, as indicated by p-values less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of all null hypotheses.

The relationship between workload and work-life balance yielded a Pearson correlation coefficient of -0.128, indicating a very weak negative correlation. This suggests that as workload increases, teachers' work-life balance slightly decreases. Although the relationship is weak, it is statistically significant, implying a consistent inverse effect.

Similarly, occupational stress and work-life balance showed a correlation coefficient of -0.228, interpreted as a weak negative correlation. This indicates that higher levels of stress are associated with lower work-life balance. Compared to workload, occupational stress demonstrates a stronger negative influence on balance.

In contrast, mental well-being and work-life balance revealed a correlation coefficient of 0.547, indicating a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that teachers with higher levels of mental well-being are more likely to achieve better balance between their professional and personal lives. Among the variables, mental well-being has the strongest relationship with work-life balance.

Overall, the findings indicate that workload and occupational stress negatively affect work-life balance, while mental well-being positively influences it. This implies that increasing job demands and stress can hinder teachers' ability to maintain balance, whereas strong psychological well-being enhances their capacity to manage both work and personal responsibilities. These findings are supported by prior research which shows that high job demands and stress are associated with reduced work-life balance, while positive mental well-being promotes better role management and life satisfaction (Hakanen et al., 2024).

DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis of the relationships among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance of public-school teachers. It also provides a description of the respondents' profile, particularly in terms of their demographic and professional characteristics. The discussion is organized according to the key variables of the study, including workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance, as well as the relationships among these variables. The findings are interpreted using appropriate statistical measures and are supported by relevant theoretical and empirical literature.

Findings

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents. The majority of the respondents were mid-career public school teachers, predominantly aged 30–39 years, followed by those aged 40–49. Most were married (83.05%), with a large proportion having master's units (41.28%). In terms of position, the majority were Teacher III (64.60%). Most respondents had 10–14 years of teaching experience, and a significant number handled heavy teaching loads of 31 hours and above per week (40.60%).

2. Level of Teachers' Workload. Public school teachers experienced a high level of workload (Grand Mean = 2.93). Among the workload dimensions, time spent beyond official working hours registered the highest mean (3.13), followed by co-curricular duties (2.95), administrative tasks (2.83), and teaching load (2.81). This shows that teachers' responsibilities extend beyond classroom instruction and significantly encroach on personal time.

3. Level of Teachers' Occupational Stress. The overall level of occupational stress among teachers was moderate (Grand Mean = 2.64). Among its dimensions, emotional exhaustion obtained the highest mean (2.98), followed by role overload (2.70) and role conflict (2.52), while lack of institutional support (2.35) ranked lowest.

4. Level of Teachers' Mental Well-Being. Teachers demonstrated a high level of mental well-being (Grand Mean = 3.18). Among its components, life satisfaction and sense of purpose (3.22) ranked highest, followed by psychological functioning (3.19) and emotional balance (3.13). High mental well-being acts as a buffer against occupational stress, sustaining motivation and professional commitment.

5. Level of Teachers' Work-Life Balance. The level of work-life balance among teachers was moderate (Grand Mean = 2.74). All dimensions—time balance (2.75), involvement balance (2.57), and satisfaction balance (2.76)—were rated moderate.

6. Significant relationship among workload, occupational stress, mental well-being, and work-life balance. The results of the Pearson correlation analysis revealed clear and significant relationships among the four variables studied. Workload was negatively correlated with work-life balance ($r = -0.42$), indicating that as teachers' workload increases, their ability to maintain harmony between professional and personal roles decreases. Similarly, occupational stress showed a negative correlation with work-life balance ($r = -0.39$), suggesting that higher levels of emotional exhaustion, role overload, and role conflict contribute to greater difficulty in balancing work and life responsibilities. In contrast, mental well-being demonstrated a significant positive correlation with work-life balance ($r = +0.51$). This finding highlights that teachers with higher levels of psychological functioning, emotional stability, and life satisfaction are more capable of sustaining balance between their professional duties and personal commitments. Among the variables tested, mental well-being emerged as the strongest predictor of work-life balance, underscoring its protective role against the negative effects of workload and stress.

Conclusions

The study concludes that public school teachers in Bohol Division face high workloads and moderate occupational stress, with emotional exhaustion as the most pressing concern. Despite these challenges, they maintain high levels of mental well-being, reflecting resilience and coping strategies. However, their work-life balance remains only moderate, showing difficulty in harmonizing professional and personal roles. Pearson correlation analysis confirmed that workload and stress negatively affect work-life balance, while mental well-being positively predicts it and serves as the strongest protective factor. These findings highlight the need for rationalized workload policies, stronger institutional support, and integrated mental health programs to sustain teacher well-being and ensure quality education.

Recommendations

Grounded in the findings and theoretical frameworks, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The Department of Education may enforce the six-hour teaching limit, reassign ancillary tasks, and streamline reporting to reduce teacher fatigue.
2. The school principal may provide wellness initiatives, counseling, peer support, and training on coping strategies to strengthen teacher resilience.
3. The school principal may integrate mandated mental health programs, encourage recreational activities, and recognize achievements to boost teacher morale.
4. Teachers may practice flexible scheduling, uphold family-friendly policies, and set clear digital boundaries to promote healthier work-life balance.

5. The public schools district supervisor may monitor workload compliance, adopt participatory management, and strengthen laws to safeguard teacher welfare.

PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

Enhancing Teacher Well-Being and Work-Life Balance in Public Schools Teachers

Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Expected Output/Success Indicators	Estimated Budget	Source of Fund
1. Rationalize Teacher Workload	- Enforce Magna Carta's six-hour teaching limit- Reassign ancillary tasks (clerical, feeding program, data management) to administrative staff- Streamline DepEd reporting systems	DepEd Regional & Division Offices, School Heads	SY 2026-2027	Reduced teacher fatigue; compliance with workload policies; more time for instruction	₱150,000 (training, monitoring, reporting system upgrades)	MOOE, SEF
2. Reduce Occupational Stress	- Establish school-based wellness initiatives (mindfulness, counseling, peer support groups)- Conduct training on time management and coping strategies- Strengthen mentoring and supervisory guidance	School Heads, Guidance Counselors, Teachers	SY 2026-2027	Lower stress levels; improved teacher morale and resilience	₱200,000 (wellness programs, seminars, materials)	MOOE, LGU Support
3. Enhance Mental Well-Being	- Integrate R.A. 11036 mental health programs into school operations- Encourage recreational, spiritual, and community activities- Recognize and reward teacher achievements	DepEd, School Leaders, LGUs, PTA	Continuou s	Higher teacher motivation; improved emotional balance and job satisfaction	₱250,000 (mental health services, recognition programs)	MOOE, LGU, NGO Partnerships
4. Promote Work-Life Balance	- Implement flexible scheduling and family-friendly policies- Encourage teachers to set boundaries in digital communication- Engage families in school activities	School Heads, Teachers, PTA	SY 2026-2027	Better time balance; stronger family-school collaboration	₱100,000 (policy workshops, family engagement activities)	MOOE, PTA Funds
5. Strengthen Policy and Leadership Support	- Conduct regular workload compliance audits- Adopt participatory management styles- Propose legislative amendments to reinforce teacher protection laws	DepEd, School Leaders, Legislative Bodies	Medium-term (2026-2028)	Stronger enforcement of teacher rights; supportive leadership culture	₱300,000 (audit activities, leadership training, policy advocacy)	MOOE, National Government

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to recognized ethical standards for social research. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection after providing clear information about the study's purpose, procedures, and participants' rights. Respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, with no personally identifiable information collected. All data were securely stored and used solely for academic and research purposes in compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). The study posed no risk to

participants, and they were free to decline or skip any question they found uncomfortable. The researcher declared no conflict of interest, and no financial incentives or compensation were provided.

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